

ANALYSIS OF THE CONNECTION OF THE DATABASE WITH THE PROGRAMS.

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Abstract. This article analyzes the methods of connecting the database with software tools. Its application value includes the improvement of practical effects, software differences and convenience. Combining the practical features of the database programming tool, this article covers the selection of database types, database creation, database storage mode selection, file protection, selection of programming tool optimization, and software system upgrade design.

Key words: Database, digital data, sql, mysql, postgresql, oracle, software tools, php, java, python, wamp, xampp, tomcat, open server and laragon servers.

АНАЛИЗ СВЯЗИ БАЗЫ ДАННЫХ С ПРОГРАММАМИ.

Аннотация. В данной статье анализируются способы подключения базы данных с помощью программных средств. Ценность его применения включает улучшение практических эффектов, различий в программном обеспечении и удобства. В этой статье, сочетающей в себе практические возможности инструмента программирования баз данных, рассматриваются выбор типов баз данных, создание базы данных, выбор режима хранения базы данных, защита файлов, выбор оптимизации инструмента программирования и проектирование обновления программной системы.

Ключевые слова: База данных, цифровые данные, sql, mysql, postgresql, oracle, программные инструменты, php, java, python, wamp, xampp, tomcat, открытый сервер и серверы laragon.

INTRODUCTION

With the continuous development of the new digital era, the scope of data storage has expanded. It can create an automated, easy-to-use and easy-to-use internal information processing system for the enterprise [1]. Currently, the work related to the digital data warehouse is developing throughout Uzbekistan, therefore, the data warehouse and software are among the large-scale systems. It then collects data and transmits it to the platform to further improve the efficiency of the targeted work. At the same time, the programming tool can perform a targeted file processing process to prevent the leakage of internal enterprise information and ensure the enterprise's profit. However, a database programming tool will need to create a software repository based on certain requirements and analyze specific programming issues for the stability of the database software. In addition, this document provides valuable information for production activities and ensures the preservation of information in the database, thereby contributing to the sustainable and harmonious development of society.

THE MAIN PART

In the construction of computer software engineering, the main construction content is the construction of the basic framework structure of the system. At the same time, based on the network operating environment, application analysis of database performance is performed to improve the standardization of the entire application system. There is a lot of work involved in the

entire process from creating a data warehouse to using it. However, the entire usage process can be controlled using a database programming tool [2].

Figure 1. Schematic diagram of the operation of the database.

As shown in Figure 1 mentioned above, after a user submits an application request, it is directly loaded into the application system. The required data is then extracted from the database management system and returned to the user to complete the data application cycle. It also effectively improves the practical effect of the data warehouse, allows to fulfill the expected requirements and increases the satisfaction of the user services [3].

Computer software database programming tool.

It covers all types of information technology and media based on computer software database programming technology, which ensures the normal operation of the information processing system and the processing of various tasks. Database programming technology helps to create and develop a computer database and plays an important role in its main features [4]. In order to ensure that the efficiency and performance of the software engineering design meet the relevant design requirements, the application direction and performance requirements must be determined before programming the data warehouse [5]. This requires software engineers to interact with users and implement actual software programming after fully understanding users' needs. First, after the needs of users, it is necessary to create a basic system framework that can meet the needs of users, fill in relevant content in real time, and increase the functional content of measurement and drawing software. Functional measuring and plotting software can resist the operation of common threats in a networked environment.

Database software connections.

Typically, database software connections are based on the following algorithm. Variables are given a name for connection. It is called localhost, username, password. The connection condition is entered into the operator, if there is an error connecting to the database, the code inside

the condition will apply the condition. If otherwise there are no errors connecting to the database, then the text output "Connected to the database" will work. The block diagram shown in Fig. 2.

Figure 2. Database connection block diagram.

An analysis of the database connection to the software is shown in Table 1 below.

Table 1.

Data warehouse software connectivity analysis and text counts.

№	Software	Number of texts
1	C++ programming language	639
2	JAVA programming language	625
3	Golang programming language	553
4	Python programming language	440
5	PHP programming language	261

Figure 3. Diagram of the code(s) written in the program.

PHP is a server-side scripting language and is a powerful tool for creating dynamic and interactive web pages. PHP is a widely used, free and effective alternative to competitors such as Microsoft ASP. Also, codes are written differently in different programs. Therefore, the diagram presented in Figure 3 differs in that the number of codes written in the PHP programming language is small and it does not select servers.

When the programs written in PHP programming language are placed on the server, they can work easily on wamp, xampp, tomcat, open server and laragon servers. Also, the use of PHP programming language in the project was found to be of the same purpose.

PHP is a great and popular language!

- ✚ It's powerful enough to be at the core of the biggest blogging system on the internet (WordPress)!
- ✚ Deep enough to manage large social networks!
- ✚ It's also very easy to become the first server language for beginners!

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, the data warehouse programming tool has a very high practical value in the design process of computer software. We can combine the practical features of a data warehouse programming tool for detailed analysis and design of various engineering parameters. On the one hand, it can improve the quality of work and work efficiency. On the other hand, this has a positive meaning for increasing the stability of the work activity stage and increasing the main competitiveness in the market.

REFERENCES

1. Zhu Jianfeng. Analysis of database programming technology strategy based on computer software engineering[J]. Computer Products and Circulation, 2020(04).
2. Masharibovich, N. O., & Narimanovich, R. O. (2023). TALABALAR UCHUN ONLINE IT SAVODXONLIGINI OSHIRISHDA MA'LUMOTLAR OMBORINING TAHLILI. Conferencea, 11-17.
3. Narimanovich, R. O., & Mirxamidovna, X. D. (2023). MA'LUMOTLAR BAZASINI O 'QITISH TIZIMIDA, QO 'LLANILADIGAN MA'LUMOTLAR BAZASINING DASTURIY MAHSULOTLARINI USULI VA TAHLILI. DENMARK" THEORETICAL AND PRACTICAL FOUNDATIONS OF SCIENTIFIC PROGRESS IN MODERN SOCIETY", 14(1).
4. Mirxamidovna, X. D., & Narimanovich, R. O. (2023). MA'LUMOTLAR BAZASINING DASTURIY MAHSULOTLARINI TAHLILI VA AFZALLIKLARI. Conferencea, 89-94.
5. Tomson L., Velling L. development Web-application PHP and MySQL. - K.: "DiaSoft", 2008. - 672 p.